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Guidelines for workshop 1

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Executive Summary

The objective of the workshop is to initiate the process of collaboratively designing a Tailored Empowerment Program (TEP). This workshop marks the first stage of a two-part series. After the initial workshop, our team of experts will develop the framework for the Tailored Empowerment Program, which will be presented, discussed, and refined further in the second workshop. Following the collective effort, a pilot program will be implemented.

The workshop's focus revolves around the geographical context of each Transition Coastal Lab (TCL) and envisions the challenges and potential solutions related to promoting environmentally friendly transformations in coastal regions by 2050. While the challenges are typically global in nature, our approach addresses them from a local perspective.

Based on the data from workshop 1, we will develop Tailored Empowerment Programs. The development of Tailored Empowerment programs involves scenario processes that entail envisioning a potential future state and determining the steps required to reach it. In the EmpowerUs initiative, our primary emphasis lies on understanding two crucial aspects: a) identifying the perceived challenges, and b) exploring potential solutions. This understanding enables us to collaboratively design a practical and realistic pilot program that effectively tackles some of these challenges, utilizing the EmpowerUs Fund. While developing the scenarios, we draw upon a methodology that has proven successful in previous instances. This approach is valuable as it allows us to explore alternative scenarios, expanding our range of observations towards the future. It also facilitates the identification of potential risks and opportunities that might not otherwise receive immediate attention or are disregarded due to their perceived unlikelihood.

Summary of steps in figure below. For more details, see the information package in SharePoint (with video, templates for power point presentations and workshop 1 report), and appendix 1 and 2.

Step	Description	Comment
Welcome	Present TCL information:	Eclipse, TCL audit, Q. Make notes if something special has happened (political, news...) will affect their state of mind.
Step 1	Stakeholders share challenges. Make time for discussions	Prepare challenges from fieldwork/task 2.1) <i>After this step we have an idea of what they perceive as main challenge and how they think about them</i>
Break/dinner/coffee	Gives facilitators time for step 2	You may not take part of break but analyse challenges.

Step 2	Split in group. They will discuss solutions to the challenges: how does their desired future look like? If necessary, introduce different jokers/black swans to each table – different scenarios. /RATHER THAN JOKERS: HOW TO BRIDGE ALL CHALLENGES	Each group will choose a person to present. One support-facilitator to take notes and make sure ground-rules are followed and dialogue is on-going. If problem with dialogue, introduce jokers.
Coffee break		
Step 3	Present group work to all. Share different solutions	May need flipchart/magic sheets
Step 4	Next steps: the EmpowerUs process: Workshop 2 and TEPs	Organizers summarize and what next

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1. Objective

The main objective of this document is to provide a thorough description of how to organize and carry out future scenario workshops. Overall, EmpowerUs aims to

- understand what **challenges** the Transition Coastal Labs (TCLs) face and create **solutions**: a possibility for alternative futures perceived as desirable at workshop 1,
- develop the individual and collective capacity to invent these desired futures through Tailored Empowerment Programs (**TEPs**) in workshop 2,
- and finally test out a **pilot** developed by each TCL.

Hence, *workshop 1 will be key to generate a knowledge base about the challenges in the TCLs both from the bottom-up (local perceptions) and top-down (from WP2, WP3 and WP4).*

The NRI team is responsible for facilitating the workshop together with the Academic Leads for each TCL, while the TCL hosts are responsible for organizing the practical aspects of the workshop.

The results from the future scenario workshops will in a very important way shape the next steps of the EmpowerUs project. They will provide the TCLs with insight on their development, opportunities, and challenges, as well as create a vision for the TCLs. What does the whole society of the TCL perceive as the most important challenges, and which are the emerging opportunities? Do they feel disempowered and how? What values do they want their future municipality to recognize and be associated with? These are important questions where input from a wide range of stakeholders that represent society is needed to develop a Tailored Empowerment Program and a pilot.

In summary, the purpose of Workshop 1 is:

- To learn together about the challenges and possibilities for TCLs faced with climate change and related policies.
- To understand how each TCL can empower themselves based on the perceived challenges and what type of solution they imagine. How can EmpowerUs support the imagined future, and what do TCLs want to happen?

The findings of Workshop 1 will be used to develop Tailored Empowerment Programmes (TEPs) and to develop a pilot (workshop 2). It is important to remind the participants that the solutions must be sustainable and line with Green Deal; and also, be clear about the limitations of EmpowerUs, including time (3-year project) and money (50 000 Euros is the funds available).

2. Future Scenario Workshops & Tailored Empowerment Programs

2.2 What are future scenarios?

Future scenarios can be defined as the systematic study of possible and preferable futures including worldviews and myths that underlie each future. There are different theoretical frameworks and foresight techniques that exist. Simply put, they can be organized in relation to the principal questions an actor may want to pose about the future: Trend analysis (or forecasting) aims to

answer the question “What will happen?”, explorative scenarios address “What can happen?” and normative scenarios ask “How can a specific target be reached?” (Börjeson et al. 2006).

For workshop 1, we focus on co-creating desired futures – or rather Tailored Empowerment Programs - to overcome the challenges to the TCL. It can be described as a mix of explorative and normative scenarios. Typically, a future scenario workshop will ask participants to think 20-50 years ahead. The scenarios are participatory as they include a variety of stakeholders and different forms of knowledges. The scenario-method is based on deliberative dialogue method. A deliberative dialogue can be defined as:

*“...a form of discussion aimed at finding the best course of action. Deliberative questions take the form 'What should we do?' The purpose is not so much to solve a problem or resolve an issue as to **explore the most promising avenues for action**. Deliberative dialogue differs from other forms of public discourse — such as debate, negotiation, brainstorming, consensus-building — because **the objective is not so much to talk together as to think together**, not so much to reach a conclusion as to discover where a conclusion might lie.” (Emphasis added, Scott London³).*

Accordingly, the goal of the discussion is to “think together” as opposed to debating. In a debate, you typically try to make an argument and convince your opponent. In a dialogue you aim to listen, explain, and understand.

Like any method, it has its strength and weaknesses. The facilitator(s) has an important role, since deliberative workshops are always open to manipulation: how the discussions and activities are framed, how the participants are introduced to the topic, and what questions are asked will all shape the results. Furthermore, power-relations are an issue that should be considered explicitly. This is done by establishing ground rules, providing a common base for understanding, including everyone in discussion and by being an active facilitator. However, it is important to understand that power-relations will always be present (before, during and after the workshop) and they will play a role in the dynamics of the dialogue. Since we are dealing with people, all issues cannot be controlled, but facilitators will be there to support the process, apply ground rules and take notes so these dynamics are accounted for. It is also important to understand that the workshop involve small numbers of people and is therefore not statistically significant and may not be representative of the views of the wider population. The persons invited to the EmpowerUs workshop are chosen based on the stakeholder mapping exercises which cover key stakeholders in the TCLs.

Based on discussions and reflections with all TCL teams and WP leads, Workshop 1 has become more focused on the developing TEPs rather than explore future scenarios. Still, this is the theoretical background for workshop 1.

³ <http://scott.london/reports/dialogue.html>

Common base of understanding:

Present EmpowerUs and baseline data from WP2 Task 2.1. and the Q results if available.

Ground Rules:

- ✓ Think freely and respect each other.
- ✓ Multitude of voices - no aim for consensus
- ✓ All voices are equally important.
- ✓ This is a learning arena.
- ✓ Chatham House rule: Cite content not people.

Other responsibilities for the facilitators:

- ✓ be aware of power-relations & take notes on dynamics during discussions.
- ✓ Make room for everybody to voice opinion while respecting the wish to remain silent.
- ✓ Ensure a good atmosphere.

3. This manual

This manual will describe in detail how to do the Future Scenario Workshop. It is of great importance that the steps of the process are followed with good representation and engagement from different actors, keeping in mind the principle of leaving no-one behind. Please use the expertise of the EmpowerUs gender and equality coordinator, RURALIS.

The suggested process is a description for carrying out a participatory process, mixing both a bottom-up and top-down approach to discover challenges and opportunities through multi-actor participation. We combine participatory approaches with information and facts about the municipality, the demographic state, coastal zone management issues and the current status of business and entrepreneurship (Van Oort et al 2015). The approach is based on a methodology developed for scenario-building in the climate change¹ context, and it combines participatory approaches with information about the global and local context.

In the following section we describe the method, process and material needed.

4. Before the workshop

Selecting stakeholders and materials needed

It is important that the invited stakeholders represent the municipality in terms of age, gender, and occupation. We want to leave no-one behind. A good idea can be to try to find participants from representative organizations such local schools (NB: special ethical requirements when including under 18), Non-Governmental Organizations, indigenous people, business representatives, public employees, elderly people etc (see the stakeholders mapping template in SharePoint under Task 3.1).

Based on previous experiences, a good number of participants is about 20 people, or a range of 15-30 people. Make sure that you start inviting well ahead.

Do not underestimate the amount of time you will spend on selecting stakeholders. It will likely be necessary to “groom” people to prioritize this type of participation. It is a good idea to be prepared with some arguments that can persuade each person to come. They need to know “what’s in it for me”? It is a good idea to make phone calls initially, then send e-mails with detailed information and ask for other names as well.

A week or so before the workshop, remind people about the event and send them a program with updated information and where and when the workshop will take place.

The engagement of the participants and what they represent is crucial for the outcome EmpowerUs for the TCL. Recall that we focus on **Users of the Sea**, defined as people living in coastal communities. This is the moment when we start the work to define what to aim for (TEPs and pilots), and therefore it is also during this process that the route for future decisions is created.

Other preparations

- Make sure you have a presentation of the EmpowerUs project and your TCL ready,
- Clarify other participants from the EmpowerUs team.
- Arrange an Eclipse/Nature Based Solution presentation. The NRI can provide you with some general slides about EmpowerUs if needed.
- Prepare relevant jokers for your TCL. Some examples are provided below.
- Watch the video prepared by ERINN (Appendix 1).

Material and resources

Before the actual workshop there are several issues that the TCL team must take care of. You will need to set a date, book a venue, prepare a presentation in relevant language and prepare the knowledge baseline. You will need more people than you think to take notes during the workshop and some to be responsible for coffee/breaks. Do not count on the person that represents/organizes the workshop, as taking notes takes too much effort and concentration. Remember that this is in many ways the key outcome from the workshop, and you will have to describe the process and context, what was said, who said it, and importantly the challenges, possibilities, and visions.

- ✓ Book a room with a projector (for presentations)
- ✓ A room for group work – depending on your main room and the number of participants
- ✓ Flipcharts/Magic Sheet: both for taking notes (on a tripod) and for hanging on the wall
- ✓ Pens and markers (for writing on flipcharts and markers for all participants to write on sticky notes)
- ✓ GDPR rules & consent forms: depending on TCL rules.
- ✓ A good camera to document the process! Make sure you take a lot of photos.
- ✓ Do not underestimate the importance of coffee and remember to order food.
- ✓ Personnel: You will need several people to take notes during the workshop.
 - Consider using professionals/students for this task, at least the person that will make the main document and coordinate all the notes.
 - You may use some of the participants that you know are up for such tasks to take notes during the discussions – but then they will not be able to participate as much because they will observe and take notes.
 - It is necessary with one person to take notes during the joint group discussions and one for each smaller group. Hence, if there are 20 people attending and 4 small groups made for discussions, you will need 4 people to take notes.

It is a good idea to prepare a folder for each participant when they arrive, with a list of participants and contact information, a program and explanation of what they are going to do. If you do this, you can also give them the sticky notes and a pen in the folder.

Tips for creating a good atmosphere

When people arrive make sure that you give everyone a folder, shake their hand, be interested, and create a nice atmosphere. Have a registration sheet ready (either digitally or printed), in order to register who actually came to the workshop.

In order to provide a backdrop or context for the workshop and give everybody a common platform we suggest:

- Make a short presentation to set the stage (introduce the workshop schedule, the EmpowerUs project)
- inform the participants of their ethical rights as participants in the project (everyone signs a consent form) and that you will take photos during the workshop (try not to include people's faces, but the activities), and that people should let you know if they do not want to be photographed.
- If there is time, it is nice for all participants to say their name and who they are, for example their role in the coastal community, their occupation or similar (30 sec).
- As discussed in the beginning of the report, it is key to frame the workshop as a deliberative dialogue and not a debate.

Ground Rules:

- ✓ Think freely and respect each other.
- ✓ Multitude of voices - no aim for consensus.
- ✓ All voices are equally important.
- ✓ This is a learning arena.
- ✓ Cite content not people.

Other responsibilities for the facilitators:

- ✓ Be aware of power-relations & take notes on dynamics during discussions.
- ✓ Make room for everybody to voice opinion while respecting the wish to remain silent (finding the balance is an art).
- ✓ Ensure a good atmosphere.
- ✓ Inform that any recording only for internal use.
- ✓ Photos: let us know if not ok.
- ✓ Informed consent: We need signed consent forms from all.

5. Executing the workshop

Preparations before starting

Prepare the venue *before* the stakeholders arrive.

- Hang up the flip charts/magic sheets, organize the room in a practical way.
- have your presentation ready.
- Prepare a folder for each participant with sticky notes, pens, EmpowerUs factsheet and the program.
- Make sure you have coffee, and registration forms ready and that each person knows what their role is.

Suggested room set up for first part of workshop: exploring challenges

You must consider the rooms you have available. The chairs can be set up in a semi-circle, or around group tables. The main point is that they all can see your presentation and are close to the flipcharts.

This is how they will sit when they brainstorm and write down the challenges. See figure 1.

Figure 1: you can organize the room in a semi-circle or with tables. You need flipcharts that participants can put sticky notes on (you will make clusters and participants will vote later). For the group session it is best with several rooms to keep the noise down. The picture is from a workshop in Kirovsk, borrowed from Bob van Oort et al 2015.

When people arrive make sure that you give everyone a folder, shake their hand, be interested, and create a nice atmosphere. Have a registration sheet ready (either digitally or printed).

Workshop part 1: Challenges

Welcome and set the stage for your TCL: 30 minutes

Make a nice, positive and including welcome. NRI representative/Host/AL will present EmpowerUs and the local team the program. Present the challenges you have prepared (posted on the wall).

Brainstorm challenges. 30 minutes

- **What challenges will impact your way of life in [TCL] the next 20-30 years?**
- **What are the key challenges?**
- **What do you want to happen?**
- **What are the major challenges to this?**

Ask them to remain seated, take out their sticky notes and write down at least three challenges in their coastal area. One challenge per sticky note since you will move the sticky notes around. The challenges can be anything: natural, social, economic – anything that is important to stakeholders. Ask them to put them on the flip charts/magic sheet and next to similar ones. Let them know that they may continue to put up sticky notes throughout the workshop if they come up with more challenges. If time, open up for a short plenary discussion/reflections on the challenges.

Take pictures of the sticky notes!

Break: 30 minutes

Presentation – data from TCL

- Short presentation from data collection in EmpowerUs so far (based on T2.1 and the Q) and key messages from Eclipse report. This may also be done as part of the introductory presentation.
- Alternatively, visiting project partners can have a short presentation (eg. about other TCLs).

Workshop part 2: Group work, possible solutions - 45 minutes

The aim is now to get the participants to create solutions for the challenges in groups. Support them in the process by asking questions: are these solutions in line with your vision of a wanted future? Why do you agree? Why do you disagree? What is missing? What has been learnt?

Instructions: Given the challenges, can you imagine how to solve these in a way that is in line with your values/your wellbeing/green change?

The aim is now to get the participants to make visions & solutions for their community. Support them in the process by asking questions, e.g., Do these visions create a good picture of a wanted future? Why do you agree? Why do you disagree? What is missing? What has been learnt?

- Organize tables where people work in groups. Ask each group to choose a “leader” to take notes and present summary for all.
- Have one note-taker per group that is not involved in the discussion. These notes must be sent to the organizers.
- When they are getting into the mindset of generating a solution, the group must try to formulate their own vision inspired by the challenges, experiences, and knowledge.
- Consider dividing the group discussion into three steps: 1. individual brainstorming, 2. sharing individual ideas within groups, 3. discuss potential overarching solutions within groups and how to get there.

Let them discuss it for a while. If they have a good discussion the facilitator does not need to intervene. If necessary, introduce “joker questions”. Recall that this is not a typical scenario workshop as we are aiming at co-creating Tailored Empowerment Programs, not scenarios as such. Still, it is useful to try to be visionary.

Questions for group discussion

Examples of support questions for finding solutions:

- What do you like about living here?
- How can we reach [TCL specific target]?
- What resources does the community hold that we could build on?

Examples of jokers if the discussion is slow:

- What if there is a Baby boom?
- What if government remove taxes for employment?
- What if the Ukraine war leads to lack of food?
- What if the key fish species moved north due to climate changes/invasive species?
- Algae bloom kills farmed fish.
- Corner stone business disappears.
- Wind power

Workshop part 3: Summary and plenary discussion - 40 minutes

Give them a short break if time before you gather everybody again.

- Each group presents their visions. What does their solution look like? How can we get there? Comments and discussions.

Give them a short break if time before making one big group again for a plenary discussion.

- Each group will present a summary of their discussion: how does their solution look like? How can we get there? Comments and discussions.
- Discuss the results: What do the stakeholders read out of this? What is significant, does something stick out? What does this indicate? Any clear messages? What did you learn?
- What was surprising?
- What are the most important messages of the day?

Next steps and goodbye: 5 minutes

Summarize the workshop. Explain what you will do with the data; that we will make TEPs and a pilot. We will make something practical and real with our EmpowerUs funds.

NB: MUST SET THE STAGE FOR ISSUES IN LINE WITH EMPOWERUS: a) must be sustainable and line with Green Deal; b) limitations are time (3-year project) and funding (50 000 Euros).

Appendix 1

EmpowerUs video guidelines for Workshop 1: [EmpowerUs Workshop 1 Guidance Video FINAL.mp4](#).

Appendix 2

Instruction for facilitators of scenario workshop

By NRI team 2023

This document gives instructions for facilitators of the first series of workshops in EmpowerUs. The methodology for the workshop combines exploratory and normative approaches with new and existing information about the local context generated fieldwork in the region. The initial idea was for the workshop to be of a purely explorative character, but based on feedback and experience from the consortium partners, we found it necessary to develop a new approach in order to avoid research fatigue.

Key elements in workshop 1:

- Present findings, including challenges
- Get the TCLs input on the challenges
- Discuss possible solutions for Tailored Empowerment Program

After this workshop, you should have data on:

- Challenges
- A range of solutions as perceived from the municipality
- Notes from participatory observations
- A range of ideas for the Tailored Empowerment Programs
- Notes to make a short report that can be shared with participants and EmpowerUs consortium.

Super-short guidelines:

1. Workshop Preparation

- Gather with your TCL team in advance to prepare.
- Assign note-takers for each workshop group.
- Put your focus question and blank posters on a wall.
- Write the challenges that you have already found in your TCL on post-its.
- Place post-its on the posters in thematic clusters.
- This is to demonstrate what you think you know after fieldwork. It also gets people in the right state of mind to add new challenges.
- Arrange tables with post-its, pens and info about EmpowerUs.

2. Introduction to EmpowerUs

- Introduce workshop participants to EmpowerUs.
- Explain the purpose and the ground rules of the workshop.
- Share what you think you already know about the TCL with participants.

3. Interactive Session – Brainstorming Challenges

- Get participants to write additional TCL challenges on post-its (already prepared some)

- Participants should be given ~10 minutes to brainstorm.
 - Participants will then place their post-its on the posters in the relevant clusters.
 - Briefly discuss the additional challenges with the participants.
4. **Break**
- Provide food if possible.
 - During the break, gather the TCL team to look at the new challenges.
 - Any surprises?
5. **Interactive Session – Group Work on Solutions**
- Participants will work in groups to explore solutions to the challenges.
 - Each group will choose a local facilitator to guide conversation (and a note-taker for EmpowerUs)
 - First, participants will write down their ideas individually.
 - Each participant will then share their ideas with their groups.
 - Each group will cluster their ideas and look for solutions that can solve multiple challenges.
 - The group will then explore what it takes to put the solutions into action.
6. **Plenary Discussion and Future Plans**
- One individual from each group will present their ideas to the wider group.
 - Members of other groups are encouraged to ask questions and discuss ideas in further detail.
 - The next steps of the project should then be presented before wrapping up.
 - This includes details about Workshop 2 and the pilot.
 - Collect all consent forms and feedback from participants.
7. **Team Debrief**
- Gather the TCL team after the workshop to have a debrief.
 - Decide on who will take the lead on the short summary report.
 - The importance of the report is two-fold (other???)
 - For sharing information with workshop participants and communities
 - To inform WP4 and the design of Workshop 2.

More details under:

Preparations

This should of course be done before the participants arrive. Put up flipcharts on the biggest wall. Position the charts as shown below (close together). Use scotch to keep the post-its there.

Figure 1: Prepare flipchart on the wall with some challenges – this is also a way to present Task 2.1 to participants. The challenges are divided into sub-challenges where possible.

Figure 2 Figure 3: example from TCL Træna after stakeholders added challenges on post-its.

The chairs can be arranged no tables in a half circle, or people can be placed in groups already from the start. This depends on the room. Have the necessary equipment for a power-point presentation.

Prepare sets of post-its and pens to each of the participants. It is a good idea to prepare files for each participants with information about EmpowerUs, the agenda and a consent form to be signed and handed in before the participants leave.

Figure 3: folders prepared for workshop 1 in TCL Træna. Pens, pencils, empowerUs information, consent sheet and more.

Prepare the challenges that you as researchers have found in the TCL: write them on post-its. The aim of this is twofold: 1) Demonstrate what we think we know after fieldwork and data collection; 2) Allow for new challenges to be added and get people in the right state of mind.

The workshop

Introduction and “what we think we know about your TCL”

Introduction of the workshop and the crew (15 min).

This is the session in which the EmpowerUs project and the workshop process is introduced. This short talk (it should be short in order to save time for actual participatory work) need to:

1. Tell the stakeholders what EmpowerUs and the workshop is all about;

2. Give them an overview of the process in the workshop and after the workshop (use the “wave” from KPH)
3. Share data/best available knowledge about TCL so far

EmpowerUs project timeline

Figure 4: EmpowerUs Timeline

Power Point examples slides are provided in the folder with

- a general introduction to EmpowerUs, the role of the Host and timeline of EmpowerUs, focusing on the pilot.
- How the Q results can be presented (see also figure 4 below)

Figure 5: example of how the Q results can be presented, focussing on the consensus.

Interactive session: Add missing challenges to the board (20-30 minutes)

Now the real participatory work starts. The lead facilitator starts with explain the working rules: *“This is an exploratory session in which we are going to try to come up with challenges in relation to the focus question. In this session all ideas are equally valid; we do not critique or discuss the ideas here. We will discuss later. You will first think for yourself 10 minutes and go around and see if there are any challenges missing. If you miss anything, write it down on a post it. One idea per post-it. Please write with capital letter and write so that we all can read. We have some reflection questions here ---”*

Leave the participants to walk around, think and write approximately 10 minutes.

After this first round there is a wall with a lot of ideas for challenges, hopefully in some clusters. Based on input, have a short discussion.

Break (30 minutes)

If possible it is good to have a longer break here, e.g. lunch or extended coffee for networking if you have time.

The core group (facilitators and perhaps one or two from the stakeholders group) gather for looking at the added challenges. Anything surprising? Anything important you have missed.

Presenting the other TCLs (5 min) and NBS (15 minutes)

In this session, all TCLs are introduced in order for the TCL to see what the other labs are working on and to feel part of a larger EU project.

The NBS input is to remind people about the Eklipse key messages.

Group work on solutions (2h)

Each of the four groups will work on possible solutions to the challenges. The main facilitator introduces the group work which consist of two parts: a) explore solutions in general and look for something that can solve multiple challenges (30 min) b) what will it take to put ideas/solutions into action (40 min). For this part, it is a good idea to have a note-taker from your team on each table to follow the discussions and take notes for the report (see Ruralis reflexions notes to prepare). The first part aims to look for a solution for multiple challenges and to get data for the TEPs. The second one is to start a process of prioritization and finding a pilot. The main facilitator explains the process:

- *Now we will work in group on how we can solve the challenges introduced before the break. Sit in your designated group. Please choose a group leader who will present a summary of your discussion. He/she will also make sure everyone has a turn. In addition, you will have a notetaker who will not participate but will take notes and can assist if any questions.*
- *1) you will think by yourself 5 minutes: do you have a solution, idea, action? Write it down on a post it. (1 or two ideas). Next, share your idea with the group. Take a tour de table: all get to share at least one idea. Put the post it in the middle of the table and explain what it is to your group.*
- *2) Together in your group, try to cluster the ideas – does any of them belong together? Can several challenges be solved by the same solution?*
- *3) choose one or two of the clusters/solutions and try to answer a) what does it take to realize the ideas?; b) start dividing them into the steps.*

Reporting and conclusion of the workshop (1h)

Each group is requested to summarize their work for all. Short discussion. Facilitator present next steps (workshop 2 and pilot). Thanks for coming.

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